

CATEGORIES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes in detail the basic concepts of foreign language teaching methods, the basic principles of foreign language teaching and the general didactic principles of foreign language teaching methods.

Those who choose to teach a foreign language as a profession are tasked with a thorough knowledge of the theory of teaching that language. The science of teaching is covered by the science of methodology, the word “methodology” is a Greek word meaning “a set of methods of doing a job in accordance with a purpose”. The term “methodology”, which is common in pedagogical communication, has three meanings. The first refers to the subject matter (e.g., “tomorrow’s first lesson is methodology”), the second is a set of methodological approaches to teaching (e.g., “I like our teacher’s methodology”), and the third is educational theory and specialization science (e.g., “the methodology is well covered in this manual”). This chapter discusses the third terminological meaning of the word “methodology”. In other words, methodology is the science of teaching a foreign language, defining “foreign language” as a subject of study, studying the activities of teachers and educators, and

mastering the achievements of other disciplines and developing their own law explores ways. According to Prof. Yefim Izrailevich Passov, the method is goal-oriented in the learning process and is a system of principles related to the types of speech activities. Hence, principles shape the method. Here, we are talking about a broad methodological direction. (Passov, 1991)

It is worth recalling the example of experiments in a number of studies on the development of foreign language teaching methods in Uzbek schools. Talented Methodist scholar Khoshimjon Soynazarov in his scientific works has given an experimental and theoretical basis for the transfer of language experience in the receptive plan (perception) of English lexical units. (Kh. Soynazarov, 2010)

Talented Methodist prof. Tojimat Khaydarovich Sattarov has developed an experimental method of active learning of foreign language grammar. (Sattarov, 2010) An exemplary experiment was conducted to

study the syntax of the German language in the Uzbek audience. In several scientific studies, experiments in the field of foreign language teaching have risen to the level of exemplary examples. Eduart Abramovich Shtulman, one of the Methodists, conducted an in-depth research on the subject of experiments. (A. Shtulman) In the sciences that study education (pedagogy and private methodology), the term “principle” also expresses specific concepts.

According to Prof. Y. I. Passov, “principle is the foundation of the so-called teaching process.” - a rule. In education, a set of different principles is described. Methodists of foreign language teaching effectively use the research of educators, but their existence cannot be recognized without change, indifference, that is, learning taking into account the subject and applying them.

The issues of application of principles in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, their scientific and theoretical substantiation attract the attention of many Methodists. Sources of foreign and domestic methodology cover controversial issues in this area. First of all, the criteria for promoting the principles of foreign language teaching methods are discussed. The first is the inappropriateness of applying this criterion to the methodology of a subject other than a foreign language, that is, the criterion of the specificity of the subject. The second is that the scientific concepts of the principle formed in the methodology of a foreign language do not apply even to related sciences, which is a criterion for the study of this field. For example, the principle of limiting difficulties may also be involved in the teaching of other subjects. Therefore, the principles of pedagogy or psychology are applied in foreign language methodology, taking into

account the specifics of this science. Just one example: the other side of the principle of limiting difficulties is also manifested in a foreign language, i.e. the principle of easy to difficult is realized without direct acceptance (remember the consonant of the tooth space), by distributing difficulties. Secondly, methodological principles are studied on the basis of these criteria. The principles of foreign language teaching methodology are not the same in content and form. Some are generalized (e.g., the principle of speech orientation), while others are very specific to the essence of the subject (e.g., the principles of teaching grammar).

Consequently, general private and special principles of foreign language teaching methodology have been developed. It should be noted that the differentiation and consistent substantiation of these principles has not been fully achieved in science. In scientific sources, the principle of the first name is unanimously recognized by all experts. The second principle recommended by G. H. Rogova, third principle occurs in the research of M. V. Lyakhovitsky. While the fourth principle is approved by most Methodists, there is a significant difference in its naming. The term “principle of accountability of the mother tongue” has been adopted in the scientific literature published in Russian or reflecting the experience of Russian schools. In the works of foreign language teaching researchers in Uzbek schools, it is used as a “principle of taking into account language experience.” This principle is so named because students learn their mother tongue and second language before a foreign language. The general principles of the methodology are:

- 1) the principle of speech orientation of foreign language teaching

2) the principle of limiting (differentiating) and integrated learning of a foreign language

3) the principle of giving priority to exercise

4) the principle of taking into account language experience

The general principles can be interpreted as follows. According to the principle of speech orientation, the educational process is organized in order to acquire a foreign language as a means of communication, that is, to develop speaking skills and competencies within the topics of the curriculum. Practical acquisition of a foreign language is achieved through speech exercises. If the amount of exercises that teach the language material is too large, the speech orientation will be impaired. Continuation of lexical, grammatical, pronunciation exercises ends with their application in speech in a foreign language. The mastery of language units is subordinated to the mastery of speech activity. Completion of the final result with the receipt/transmission of information in a foreign language is a prerequisite for the principle of practical orientation. Among the general principles, the consideration of language experience is of particular importance. Events in which the learner has already mastered the native language and the second language, as well as the foreign language itself, can be a facilitating or

resisting factor in the presentation of new material. The three languages that come into contact in the reader's mind collide at the levels of operation, movement, and activity. In other words, previously acquired language abstraction, skill, and speech skills have a negative/positive effect on the language being studied. In short, the accumulated language experience should be taken into account in the acquisition of future speaking skills and competencies. Information about the positive (transposition) or negative (interference) transfer of speech skills should be taken into account when creating a system of exercises, and students are not informed about them in the learning process. The more or less effort and time spent is determined by the ease or difficulty of the language unit.

The use of game technology in German lessons increases the interest and activity of students in the lesson, has a positive effect on the effectiveness of the lesson. The use of educational games in the classroom allows students to master the language material and create a free psychological environment during the lesson. Before giving examples of games, we consider it appropriate to get acquainted with the materials on games and game types in the methodological literature in German.

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